

Functional sentinel system (wearable/app)

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
1.1. Purpose of the document	5
1.2. Structure of the document	5
2. Wearable devices	6
2.1. Device selection and overview	6
2.2. Data Flow	7
2.3. Server Architecture	8
2.4. Participants' connection with Garmin	11
3. Gamified application	14
3.1. General Description	14
3.2. Incentives	16
3.3. Requirements	20
3.4. Mock-ups	21
4. Dashboard	25
4.1. General Description	25
4.2. Requirements	25
4.3. Mock-ups	26
5. Technical Architecture	27
5.1. List of Components	27
5.2. Mobile Application	27
5.3. Dashboard & REST API	28
5.4. Ingestion Service (Health Questionnaires)	28
5.5. Security	29
6. Deployment Information	31
6.1. Timeline	31
6.2. Testing	31
7. Data protection & privacy considerations	34
ANNEX A	37

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

This document presents the main elements of the SynAir-G sentinel system which purpose is to gather to gather health data from the cohort and be monitored during the experiments of the project.

Health data from the cohort will be monitored by a specifically designed gamified application, as well as by wearable trackers. The app captures input from the participants at large, while the trackers accurately, continuously, and remotely, monitoring heart rate, steps, SpO2 and sleep as well as on demand activity tracking.

Sentinel data are accessible via the dashboard and will be processed in WP6 for further analysis of causality.

1.2. Structure of the document

The document is organized into the following sections:

- Section 2 – Wearable devices: provides an overview of the wearables device selected for tracking the health data from cohort, the data flow and the basic technical aspects on server configuration
- Section 3 – Gamified Application: presents the requirements, the design and the mock-ups of the developed Application.
- Section 4 – Dashboard: presents the requirements, the access levels and the mock-ups of the dashboard that will access the teachers and the cohort managers.
- Section 5 – Technical Architecture: outlines the architecture and the key components of the system.
- Section 6 – Deployment information: explains how the system deployed and the testing process followed by the testing users.
- Section 7 – Data protection and privacy considerations: provides the main lines that was followed as the project handles data of EU citizens and it is important to ensure the requirements of GDPR

2. Wearable devices

2.1. Device selection and overview

Wearable Device Selection and Criteria

During the initial steps of development, we identified a set of criteria with the rest of the cohort to guide the selection of a suitable wearable device for our study. Our focus was on continuous and real-time monitoring of heart rate, steps, SpO2 and sleep as well as on demand activity tracking. Comfortable fit on the wrists of 8-9-year-old participants and durability to withstand a four-year study period were key considerations. Constant GPS connectivity, body temperature and blood pressure were desired but not required.

Candidate Wearables and Evaluation

During the thorough selection process, we identified 6 candidate wearable devices from brands Xiaomi, Huawei, Samsung, Fitbit and Garmin. The devices from Xiaomi and Huawei were excluded due to lack of publicly available data APIs. The Samsung device was excluded due to its fragility, not suited to the study's demands. Among the remaining options, the comparison focused on Fitbit and Garmin. It was found that Garmin devices offer better overall accuracy in the desired metrics (citation). Additionally, Garmin's 24/7 European customer support was a significant advantage compared to American-Based Fitbit's.

Selection of Garmin vívosmart 5

The Garmin vívosmart 5 (Figure 1) was selected as the optimal wearable for our study. While meeting all the inclusion criteria, the device also provided extra metrics like stress levels and body battery, enhancing the depth of data collected.

The vívosmart excels in practicality featuring a 10.5 mm x 18.5 mm OLED screen and a rugged design suitable for our study's long-term requirements.

Being an off the shelf device and not a scientific one it is already extensively tested and proven to be working in all operating conditions. At the same time updates are provisioned by the company as soon as a bug is identified.

The wearable requires to be connected to a smartphone either with Android 7.0 or greater or IOS 15.0 or higher in order to sync its data. The synchronization is performed using the Garmin Connect App. The process is described in detail in a subsequent section.

FIGURE 1 GARMIN VIVOSMART 5

2.2. Data Flow

Garmin uses a push Service that allows partners to receive near-real-time updates of Garmin user data without delay or duplication associated with regularly scheduled update jobs.

User Data Synchronization Process

The initial step in this process involves the user launching the Garmin Connect app. The app automatically starts the synchronization and the user must wait until the green bar at the upper right circle is filled green (Figure 2). Through this synchronization, the app takes charge of uploading the recorded metrics to Garmin's dedicated server.

FIGURE 2 AN ONGOING SYNCHRONIZATION (LEFT), AND A SUCCESSFUL SYNCHRONIZATION (RIGHT).

Data Transmission from Garmin's Server to SynAir-G server

Subsequently, Garmin's server takes over, orchestrating the next phase of the data flow. When new data is available it carries out HTTP POST requests to a predefined callback page. Every metric has its own POST request with a JSON payload that contains the updated data (Figure 3).

```
{
  "epochs": [
    {
      "userId": "4aacafe82427c251df9c9592d0c06768",
      "userAccessToken": "8f57a6f1-26ba-4b05-a7cd-c6b525a4c7a2",
      "summaryId": "x153a9f3-5a9478d4-6",
      "activityType": "WALKING",
      "activeKilocalories": 24,
      "steps": 93,
      "distanceInMeters": 49.11,
      "durationInSeconds": 840,
      "activeTimeInSeconds": 449,
      "startTimeInSeconds": 1519679700,
      "startTimeOffsetInSeconds": -21600,
      "met": 3.3020337,
      "intensity": "ACTIVE",
      "meanMotionIntensity": 4,
      "maxMotionIntensity": 7
    }
  ]
}
```

FIGURE 3 A POSSIBLE STRUCTURE OF THE JSON PAYLOAD

Data Processing on SynAir-G’s backend

Upon reception, the server’s backend sends an HTTP 200 status (OK) and begins interpretation of the JSON payload. The first field of the JSON denotes the metric received and it indicates the collection where the data will be inserted. Then, the server performs an upsertion of the data in the appropriate mongoDB collection using as key the “userID” token and upserts based on the day field (not shown in Figure 3).

Failure and Manual Data Request

In essence, this data flow mechanism is designed to eliminate needless requests from the partner to the Garmin servers reducing the overall complexity of the systems. The push service ensures that new data is always made available. The service incorporates a retry logic, meaning that if the HTTP POST request is met with a status other than 200 (OK), the server will retry after a specific time. Each time a retry is performed the time before retrial will be greater.

While this retry logic is sufficient for the majority of downtimes experienced in servers, in an event of a major multi-day downtime a manual backfill request is available as an option from Garmin’s API tools. Using this tool the partner can request all available metrics for a user to be sent again with the service. If that is not sufficient, speaking with a Garmin representative, a partner can request multiple metrics for multiple users to be resent.

Data flow diagram

FIGURE 4 THE DATA FLOW AS DESCRIBED IN THE PREVIOUS SUBSECTIONS

2.3. Server Architecture

The server architecture forms the backbone of the data processing and storage infrastructure that will be used for the duration of the experiments. The chosen infrastructure is built upon an Amazon EC2 instance running Ubuntu, ensuring near 24/7 availability and delivering a robust platform to build upon.

Overall Server Architecture

A high level depiction of the overall server architecture is presented in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5 THE OVERALL SERVER ARCHITECTURE FOR WEARABLES

Containerization for Robust Deployment

To enhance robustness, facilitate deployment, all applications hosted on the server are containerized using Docker. Using this approach, an app and its dependencies are encapsulated, allowing deployment on any system at any time. Also, by using global variables, apps that are developed by multiple cohort members can be asynchronously updated and tested. Finally, in the event of failure, Docker ensures that all the containers will be restarted and connect with each other without any user intervention.

MongoDB database and Backend App

At the heart of the server a mongoDB container is deployed with 2 Docker volumes. The first one contains the initialization script for the database; it ensures that only certified users can add to the database and only one defined admin can perform dangerous operations, such as deleting, renaming etc. The second volume pertains to the data saved to the database. By binding a server folder to the dockered database data we ensure data persistence in case of a container restart (e.g. Server reboot).

Along the database a containerized backend application is deployed to handle incoming POST requests from Garmin servers. It was developed using the PHP programming language in a XAMPP environment. It acts as the intermediary between the data sent by Garmin servers and the storage within the mongoDB database. In order for the PHP scripts to communicate with the database, the mongoDB PHP driver was installed from PECL (PHP Extension Community Library) and in order to provide the full API for executing commands, queries and write operations, the MongoDB PHP Library was installed using Composer. The containerized app has also a volume in which the SSL certificates that enable HTTPS resign (discussed in the following subsection). The server runs the Apache 2.0 server software.

HTTPS and Domain Configuration

Garmin mandates that endpoints used for communication employ the HTTPS protocol for enhanced security. That means an SSL certificate issued by a third-party trusted provider must be used. Consequently, the setup necessitated the reservation of a unique domain for the server, since the domain given by Amazon is not valid for certification. The domain name chosen and registered is garmin.synairg.eu.

The SSL certificate is obtained through Let's Encrypt, a widely recognized certificate authority that issues free certificates. The installation process is orchestrated through Certbot, which automates the procedure of acquiring and installing the certificate. To ensure the certificate remains valid, a recurring cron job was defined to run Certbot and renew it prior to its 90-day expiration. The certificates are stored in a local server folder and are available to the server using a Docker volume.

Partner verification with Garmin

Each app using Garmin's API requires a consumer key and secret. The consumer key is used to uniquely identify a partner and the consumer secret is used to validate that the requests received are from that partner and not a third party that has gained unauthorized access to the consumer key.

Consumer key credentials are created using the Developer Portal and creating Apps. Each app represents a unique Consumer Key. The first app generated will have an evaluation-level consumer key that is rate-limited and is used for testing, evaluation and development. In order for a partner to obtain a production-level key, a verification process must be performed, using again the Developer Portal.

During the verification process a series of tests are performed. More specifically;

- The Endpoint Setup Test: This test checks the validity of the enabled endpoints. A partner must have at least the deregistration and 1 other endpoint enabled.
- The endpoint Coverage Test: This test checks the enabled endpoints for data. All of them must have data in the last 24 hours.
- The Active User Test: This test checks if there are at least 2 users that have provided data in the last 24 hours.
- The HTTP Test: This test checks for HTTP errors in the last 24 hours.
- The Ping Test: This test checks for unanswered ping notifications in the last 24 hours.
- The Pull Test: This test checks for unprompted pull notifications in the last 24 hours.

Having all the tests completed successfully, an application for a Production Key was made. The final app is without any restrictions.

2.4. Participants' connection with Garmin

Upon receiving the wearable, the guardian must perform a two-fold setup. First, the wearable must be paired to a Smartphone using the Garmin Connect App. Then the Garmin Account must be paired to the SynAir-G app.

Wearable setup

After the participant powers on the wearable for the first time, it shows a prompt to use the Connect app. The participant's guardian must perform the steps described below:

1. Select "Create Account"
2. Enter email and select "I am at least 16 years old".
3. Select date of birth using 2007 as the year.
4. Follow the next instructions and set up your wearable.
5. After setting up, from the home screen select the wearable icon from the upper right corner.
6. From the wearable screen select "Activity Tracking".
7. From Activity Tracking screen select Pulse Ox
8. From Pulse Ox screen enable "All-Day Pulse Ox".

The steps are also described in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6 STEPS FOR WEARABLES SETUP.

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Garmin Account pair with SynAir-G App

After setting up the wearable with the connect app the guardian must then pair the account created with the SynAir-G app.

Using the corresponding button in the SynAir-G app, the guardian will be redirected to a Garmin sign in page. After that the following steps must be performed:

1. Login using created account credentials.
2. Keep all available switches on and select “Save”
3. Select “Agree”

The steps are also described in Figure 7.

FIGURE 7 STEPS FOR SETTING UP THE WEARABLE AND PAIRING WITH SYNAIR-G APP

We have to note that the screenshots were taken in an early development phase so some elements may have been changed. The core functionality however remains unchanged.

3. Gamified application

3.1. General Description

Within the activities of T2.2., INLECOM undertaken the design, development and delivery of a gamified application, named Save The World, which will mainly encourage the participation to the health outcome assessment questionnaire designed for the SynAir-G cohort on a daily (minimum) or weekly (maximum) basis.

SavetheWorld can be considered as an educational application designed to engage students in the world of environmental health and societal sustainability. With the goal of encouraging students to actively participate in learning about the impacts of pollutants in Europe, SavetheWorld offers an approach to education through gamification. The main objective of SavetheWorld is to engage students in a set of activities providing incentives for answering health questionnaire specifically designed for their participation in the cohort studies in countries around Europe.

The application content aims to empower students requesting them to tackle real-life environmental & societal challenges in a thrilling and interactive gaming experience. As they play, participants will mainly gain valuable insights into the various pollutants & problems affecting European cities and the importance of adopting eco-friendly & practices and measures to enhance the wellbeing of EU citizens. Through intuitive gameplay mechanics, students must navigate through multiple levels/cities, each presenting distinct scenarios described as quests. Their mission is to save the city from impending disaster by engaging in a set of mini games, having as an end goal to combat the problem's adverse effects. In the aforementioned mini games students encounter various challenges that require critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

SavetheWorld will cater to a diverse audience by releasing the game in six languages: Greek, German, French, English, Georgian, and Finnish. By offering the application in multiple languages, students from different linguistic backgrounds can enjoy the game and learn about environmental & societal challenges in their native tongues, enhancing comprehension and engagement. It is accessible by mobile phone (iOS and Android), tablet, or computer, through parental consent.

The key characteristics of the application are summarized below:

Traveling around Europe and tackling environmental & societal challenges

The heart of SavetheWorld lies in its captivating gameplay, which takes participants on a journey across six different stages representing various countries in Europe. Each stage presents a unique environment, cultural background, and specific environmental & societal challenges. As players progress through the game, they will engage in playing mini games in order to resolve the challenges within each country.

Unlocking Cities/Levels

To progress in the game, players must actively answer health-related questions & play mini games. By doing so, they unlock access to various cities within each country. The educational content is seamlessly integrated into the game, providing students with essential environmental & societal facts and insights about the city and the specific challenges it faces. This approach fosters a sense of curiosity and a desire to learn while players enjoy the gaming experience.

To promote consistent and balanced gameplay, a level will be unlocked after a participant has been engaged 5 times with it. This feature encourages regular engagement with the application while ensuring that students do not become overwhelmed with content. The gradual unlocking of levels also helps maintain excitement and anticipation throughout the gaming journey.

Quests

The app quests are specific objectives or challenges designed to engage users and encourage them to interact with the application in various ways. During the application design, it was considered that the inclusion of quests in an app will enhance user retention, motivation, and overall user experience.

In this regard, a total of 30 (5 per country) quests has been created connected with specific cities and addressing the environmental & societal challenges they face.

For making the app and quests content easier to follow for the users, all the quests have been translated in the 6 languages that the research centers originate from. For the app testing, the translation activities also cover the Swedish language, so that partner LTU test the application and provide feedback to the development team.

Mini Games

Within each level, a series of mini-games will be available for players to enjoy. The application offers a variety of mini games carefully designed to cater to a wide variety of challenges, targeting different personalities, and ensuring users are consistently satisfied with fresh and engaging content. These games are not only entertaining but also contribute to a well-rounded skill improvement for players, by enhancing cognitive, math, decision-making, problem-solving, and imagination abilities.

New mini games will be introduced periodically. Players can customize their gaming journey by selecting games that align with their interests, ensuring they are continually engaged and satisfied.

Parent Access and Involvement

SavetheWorld recognizes the significance of parental involvement in a child's playing journey. As such, parents will have also access rights that enable them to answer the health questions on behalf of their children without playing/engaging with the game.

Scalability and Expansion

SavetheWorld's versatility allows for easy expansion with the addition of more countries, stages, and levels in the future. In this regard, the application can be updated to include fresh content and provide continuous learning opportunities.

Health questionnaire

The questionnaire is one of the most important parts of the application and expects multiple daily visits. The questionnaire will have multiple choice & slider based questions related to the wellbeing and health status of the participants.

The below questions compose the health questionnaire of the application:

TABLE 1 HELTH QUESTIONNAIRE

General health	Answers	Respiratory health	Answers
Did you go to school today?	Yes/No		
How are you today?	very bad, bad, neutral, good, very good	Do you have a cold?	Yes/No
How is your health today?	the worst health/the best heath (VAS)	Do you have symptoms of:	
How much body pain or discomfort do you feel today?	no pain /unbearable pain (VAS)		
		runny, stuffy nose	Yes/No
		cough	
		dyspnea	
		sore throat	
			if yes Visual Analogue Scale in each symptom appears

The above questions have been translated in all 6 languages with the support of the research centers, so it would be easier for the users to respond to them.

3.2. Incentives

User engagement plan

One of the initial parts of the gamified application design was the features needed to keep the users engaged in the process. The latter was implemented under the direction of the social scientists of LTU who focus on citizen science and how to motivate users to adopt the system through gamification methods.

In this regard and as first step for the design, INLE with LTU focused on understanding what motivates end-users to engage in, adopt and use the application. Hence, a Living Lab approach was adopted which is based on end-user engagement and inclusion in innovation activities of technical, social and/or socio-technical character. In Living Lab activities, end-users are engaged in their specific real-world context to ensure that a deep and contextually relevant understanding of their situation is gained, which is used as a foundation for the development of the gamified application. Thus, to increase children’s awareness on several topics and alter their behaviour, we have considered their engagement not only as physical engagement, but also preparing them about their engagement process by giving them knowledge about the activity in their own setting. The table below summarises

the overall framework for user engagement that was used, which is visualized in Figure 8 in three main engagement phases, namely, plan, act and reflect.

TABLE 2 USER ENGAGEMENT IN LLS

	User engagement in Living Labs					
Nature of engagement	Tacit (internal) engagement			Explicit (external) engagement		
User engagement phases	Cognitive engagement			Realize engagement	Engagement commitment	
Five steps in innovation decision process	Knowledge	Persuasion	Decision	Implementation	Confirmation	

FIGURE 8 ENGAGEMENT PHASES

Within the process, we also considered the barriers for the for long term user engagement as it can be seen in the table below:

TABLE 3 LONG TERM ENGEEMENT PLAN

	Engagement planning			Actual engagement	Engagement commitment
	Knowledge	Persuasion	Decision	Trial test	Confirmation
Innovation-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of technical skills to work with the innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dislike the idea of the innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data security concerns Data Privacy concerns Compatibility of innovation with the context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usability Functionality Problem with installation Disappearing novelty aspect of innovation Compatibility of innovation with the context Technological complexity User interface 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High resource consumption Mistrust of immature innovation Cost of use Interoperability Reliability of the produced data
Context-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unclear terms and conditions Lack of ealthtion about the existence of the innovation Data ownership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perceived isolation ealth concerns for the home environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health concerns for the home environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of real-time support Employing users' own resources for engagement Compatibility of innovation with the context Mobility (availability and accessibility) Health concerns Interoperability with other platforms in users' daily lives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of physical support Mistrust of activity organizers Unclear contact point Lack of interaction with humans Mobility (availability and accessibility)
User-related	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital literacy Lack of technical skills to work with the innovation Data ownership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No benefit to the innovation Procedural complexity Stigma Time-consuming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Privacy Social acceptance Lack of standards No financial compensation or prize 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of time Forgetfulness Employing users' own resources for engagement Cost of engagement Fun aspects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unclear data ownership Forgetfulness Stigma Data security concerns Unclear Rol Lack of standards

The common perspectives on citizen engagement encompass various dimensions. Firstly, citizens are viewed as sensors or monitors, contributing valuable data and insights to city systems. Additionally, citizens play a role as data and content providers, enriching the information available to urban frameworks. However, a notable absence exists in terms of co-creation, where citizen engagement within design processes is scarcely documented. Moreover, citizen needs often lack emphasis, with their requirements not being adequately outlined in development and innovation projects. In many

cases, citizens are primarily engaged in the testing of products and services, if involved at all in this capacity.

In SynAir-G project, we try to follow user engagement principles in Living Lab context as much as possible. First and foremost, engagement should be a voluntary choice for users. It's important to consider diversity – try to involve different types of users to bring out unique perspectives. Inclusivity matters, so we should make sure to include people of various groups. For example, we have tested the app with kids from different countries with different cultural background. We must also look for users who are open to change and good at working with others. It is important to also strive for a balance between genders; involving both males and females leads to a more well-rounded approach, considering both technical aspects and human needs. Lastly, when selecting users, aim for a mix of expertise levels in the field of innovation. That is why, in the app development process, we included both kids and parent for feedback and revision.

Following the abovementioned principles, SavetheWorld implemented a comprehensive reward system and incentives to motivate participants to actively engage in completing surveys. By implementing a well-designed reward system and incentives, the application aims to foster active participation from users in completing questionnaires. The token economy, energy tokens, push notifications, achievements, and skill points together form a holistic approach to engage users, promote healthy competition, and enhance the overall user experience. Through these measures, the project partners aim to create an enthusiastic community of students who actively contribute to our data collection efforts.

The details of the employed approach are presented in the paragraphs below.

Token Economy System

The heart of our incentive structure lies in the token economy system. Participants will be rewarded with energy tokens for completing the health questionnaire. These energy tokens serve as the primary currency in the application for being able to play the mini games. To maintain balance and prevent exploitation, the energy tokens will be capped at a maximum tokens per participant.

Upon successfully completing the questionnaire, participants will receive an energy token as a bonus reward. This reinforces a sense of accomplishment and encourages users to continue participating actively.

Time-based Restrictions

To prevent survey fatigue and maintain data accuracy, participants will not be able to answer the questionnaire within a certain period after their last input. This feature ensures that users take surveys thoughtfully and do not rush through them just for rewards. The cooldown period also helps in spreading out survey responses, providing a more balanced data collection process.

Profile Display

A profile page is available for each user, showcasing their progress on the game as well as the activities needed until he/she levels up.

In addition to the incentives provided to students, teachers and research centers will be able to monitor the engagement with the app and implement intervention when needed.

3.3. Requirements

Following discussions with the research centers, the following list of requirements has been drafted in order to guide the implementation process. The type of requirements created were connected with authentication, user, deployment and interfacing aspects of the application.

TABLE 4 APP REQUIREMENTS

ID	Requirement
REQ 1	Users must use an appropriate device (smartphone or tablet) that uses Android or iOS
REQ 2	Users can request support on their account concerning any difficulty / problem that may occur during the use of the app
REQ 3	Users should download the app from the app/play store and installs it
REQ 4	User should not provide any personal information during the registration process
REQ 5	Users will be provided with a username and password, upon the initialisation of the mobile application
REQ 6	Be available in all 6 languages
REQ 7	Mobile application must be deployed to AppStore or Google Play Store for iOS or Android respectively
REQ 8	User Interface must be ease of use and self-explanatory
REQ 9	Assure parents that no personal information about their children will be collected without consent, adhering to privacy and data protection regulations.
REQ 10	Include a simple tutorial and on-screen prompts to guide children through the gameplay and offer help whenever needed.
REQ 11	Include catchy and child-friendly background music, sound effects, and voiceovers to enhance the gaming experience.
REQ 12	Utilize bright and colorful graphics, animations, and characters that are appealing to children and visually stimulating.
REQ 13	The game should be suitable for children within a specific age range, ensuring that all content, visuals, and themes are appropriate and non-violent.
REQ 14	The interface should be easy to navigate and understand, with large and clear buttons or icons for young children to interact with.
REQ 15	Incorporate educational aspects

REQ 16	Ensure that the game encourages healthy gaming habits
REQ 17	Optimize the game's performance to maintain smooth gameplay
REQ 18	The game should support multiple devices (e.g., smartphones, tablets, PCs), so it should enable seamless synchronization of progress and settings across devices.
REQ 19	Provide offline capabilities for the questionnaires
REQ 20	Adhere to strict data privacy guidelines and avoid collecting sensitive information about children. Ensure that all data is securely encrypted and stored.
REQ 21	Implement an automatic save feature to record a child's progress and ensure they can continue playing from where they left off.
REQ 22	Ensure that the game's user interface adapts to different screen sizes and resolutions, providing an optimal experience across various devices.
REQ 23	Include appropriate legal disclaimers and terms of service in the game application to protect the developers and users.
REQ 24	Use secure authentication methods to prevent unauthorized access to user accounts and ensure that only legitimate users can access the game
REQ 25	Use secure network protocols (e.g., HTTPS) for communication between the game application and servers to protect data during transmission.
REQ 26	Maintain a secure and robust server infrastructure to handle user data
REQ 27	Mini Games should include an explanatory note /guidance

3.4. Mock-ups

The development of an application dedicated to an audience of children aged 8-10 years, needs a lot of careful consideration when it comes to its design and layout. Overall, the gamified application's mockups are designed with children's interests and needs in mind. They feature captivating visuals, intuitive interfaces, and age-appropriate content to create an enjoyable, educational, and safe digital playground for the users.

FIGURE 9 SYNAIR-G APPLICATION DESIGN

In this regard, the application was designed with playful letters. The background showcases the blue sky. Simple and easy-to-read buttons allow children to start the app or access various sections.

- **Main Interface:** The main interface maintains a cheerful and colorful theme with a cartoony landscape. The layout is clean and intuitive, with large icons or images to help children navigate effortlessly.
- **Characters:** The app can include lovable and diverse characters that guide children throughout the activities. These characters are cute animals which unlock as the player progresses.
- **Color Palette:** Light colours have been used mainly.
- **Sound:** Sound is an essential part of the app's graphics. Sound effects and background music are cheerful and catchy, enhancing the overall experience and keeping children engaged.

The graphics of the application aim to create an immersive and delightful experience for children. The combination of bright colors, lovable characters, interactive elements, and engaging animations ensures that the app is visually appealing, fun, and age-appropriate.

The design (Figure 9) and layout (Figure 10) of the mobile application pages are intended to guide the user through the app in a clear and intuitive manner.

FIGURE 10 SYNAR-G SCREENS

SynAir-G is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101057271. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. **Welcome Screen:** The welcome screen sets the tone for the app with a cheerful and inviting design. It features a vibrant background showcasing the earth on a playful and colorful tone.
2. **Login – Signup Page:** To use the application, the participants are required to sign-up / log-in to the application. The log-in page is the first page the participant will see. The login – signup page follows a visual appealing, user friendly, and consistent to the rest of the application design.
3. The subsequent page is the "**Sign Up**" page, where first-time users can create their accounts.
4. Another important page is the "**Main Menu Page**" which serves as a welcoming environment for the user and provides access to the app's menu. This is the main page of the application. From here the user are able to navigate to the questionnaire the profile page, settings and logout. On the top of the page, the user can find the progress tracking composed by a child-friendly dashboard that displays the child's level progress and energy points earned. It uses colorful progress bar, and encouraging messages to celebrate milestones and motivate kids to keep advancing in the app.
5. **User Profile Page:** This is a page that contains information on several user related information. Upon entering the profile page, children can choose their avatars.
6. **Europe Map:** The game journey begins with the map of the continent of Europe. This is a scrollable map of Europe in the style of a colorful map with intriguing drawings. Above the map, information related to the user are displayed (level, user profile pic, energy points etc). On the map several points indicate the user's journey on the countries of the continent. The different countries are displayed with borders and selecting a country will highlight the country area. A visual indicates the progress of the player in each country.
7. **Countries Maps:** For each country of the continent a map was created. In this map several cities' stories are featured. Each city has a navigation point with two states (locked, available) indicating its status. The avatar (user profile icon) feature is available in this section with the dialog boxes.
8. **Quests page:** In the city section, the user is presented with a storyline / quest. With the help of images and dialog boxes the informative quest related to each city is presented. For this reason, an interface with image borders and dialog boxes was created.
9. **Mini Games List Page:** This page consists of a list of all available to play games along with a pop up window that contains instructions for the game. Each mini-game has its own mockup, illustrating the gameplay, controls, and objectives. Whether it's a puzzle, memory game, coloring activity, or a creative task, the mockups entice children with vibrant graphics and intuitive instructions.
10. **Settings Page:** The settings page is available from the top right button on the main page and contains several application related settings (language selection, sound, etc).

4. Dashboard

4.1. General Description

To facilitate seamless management and monitoring of student progress, an admin and tracking dashboard has been created. This dashboard is accessible to teachers and research centers, allowing them to track the students' performance and identify areas of improvement for each participant. This feature ensures that educators and researchers can actively contribute to enhancing the cohort performance.

The said dashboard provides various functionalities to enhance the user experience, monitor performance, and manage the cohort study connected with the application effectively. Based on the needs of the research centers, three (3) main roles have been identified as dashboard users:

- Superadmin. The superadmin has access to all the information and data provided through the application. He/She can create and delete users. Superadmin role on the dashboard has been assigned to NKUA and INLE.
- Admin: Each research center from the 6 countries that the cohort study will take place has admin role rights. The admin rights include the creation of the users, the deletion of users, monitoring of the performance and the relevant metrics connected with the users on national level (as described in the user analytics section below).
- Teacher: The teacher role only has access to the statistics of the group of users assigned to it.

Overall, the dashboard connected with an app serves as a powerful tool for app administrators, and the developers' (technical) team, to manage, analyze, and optimize the application's performance, the user experience and the collection of the necessary data for the cohort study.

4.2. Requirements

More specifically, the dashboard, besides the roles analyzed in the previous chapter, has been created with the following requirements as agreed with the research centers:

User Analytics

The dashboard collects and presents user analytics, such as the number of active and non-active users, presenting the engagement metrics. This information helps the administrators understand the audience and make data-driven decisions to improve the app's performance. The statistics/charts/graphs that the dashboard offers are connected with the following queries:

1. How many users have responded (or completed) the first questionnaire.
2. List and number of the users that have not responded to the questionnaire for more than 24hours.
 - Pie chart for single day queries
 - Line chart for multi-day queries
3. Table including the questionnaire answers on a daily level. The information here can be filtered by Teacher or Research Center.

User Management

The dashboard offers users management capabilities, enabling administrators to add, remove, or edit user accounts, and access user-related data. Bulk student creation is offered through the dashboard.

The dashboard offers bulk new app users' creation (parsing excel file with id, teacher or class), adds registration code or username and password to every line and triggers downloading.

In case a study participant wants to be excluded from the cohort study, the admin can delete all the registered data/answers provided from the beginning of the study.

4.3. Mock-ups

Schools Management Interface

NAME	LAT	LON	COUNTRY
School 1	38.05305177731336	23.63956468415919	Greece
School 2	37.118101463071696	21.83383693516643	Greece
School 3	35.36441793830605	24.987257426584875	Greece
ewgr	38.256124662480348	24.808865349432352	Greece
School 4	40.68056998969455	22.97004297346703	Greece

Analytics Interface

Start Date: 31/08/2023 | End Date: 01/09/2023 | User Id: [dropdown] | Questions: [dropdown] | SUBMIT

USER	QUESTIONNAIRE	TIME
student2	health_questions	11/08/2023, 11:22:57
student2	health_questions	11/08/2023, 11:34:10
student2	health_questions	11/08/2023, 11:35:49
student2	health_questions	11/08/2023, 12:11:41
student3	health_questions	11/08/2023, 12:12:47

FIGURE 11 SYNAIR-G DASHBOARD SCREENS

5. Technical Architecture

5.1. List of Components

SYNAIR-G consists of the following components:

- Mobile App
 - Ionic v5, Angular v13, Progressive Web app, Android, IOS
- Keycloak Authentication & Authorization. OAuth2.
- Monitoring Dashboard & Rest Api
 - Nextjs, React v26, Django, Mongo DB
- Health Questionnaire Ingestion Service – Django, Mongo DB

The Figure 12 presents the overall technical architecture of the SynAir-G application & dashboard.

FIGURE 12 APPLICATION & DASHBOARD OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

5.2. Mobile Application

For the mobile application Ionic Native is used. Ionic Native is an open-source typescript framework for building mobile apps for iOS and Android. It allows developers to use Angular, a JavaScript library for building user interfaces, to build mobile apps in a single codebase that have the same look and feel as native apps written in Swift or Java. Ionic Native uses components as building blocks, which allows for better performance and a more native-like feel for the end user. The application also has PWA (progressive web app) functionalities. PWAs allows for faster, more reliable, and more engaging version of a website or eCommerce store. PWAs also provides offline operation, access the user's camera and microphone, if necessary, GPS, and more.

Ionic Native offers the following advantages:

1. Cross-platform development: Ionic Native allows developers to build mobile apps for both iOS and Android using the same codebase, which can save time and resources.
2. Reusable code: Developers can use the same code for different platforms, and even reuse code from web apps.

3. Strong community: Ionic Native has a large and active community, which means there are plenty of resources and third-party libraries available to help developers build their apps.
4. Open source: Ionic Native is open source, which means it is free to use and developers can modify the code as per their needs.

There are two deployments provided for the mobile application:

- A native deployment for iOS and Android devices which is available in the corresponding App Stores.
- A web version of the application is also deployed here <https://synairg.inlecom.eu/#/auth/login>, but can be installed as native application also from the google and Appstore.

5.3. Dashboard & REST API

The dashboard is accessible here: <https://synairg-dashboard.inlecom.eu>.

For the dashboard development Nextjs is used. Next.js is a React framework used to build full-stack web applications. React Components are used to build user interfaces, and Next.js is implemented in case additional features and optimizing actions are needed. Next.js also abstracts and automatically configures tooling needed for React, like bundling, compiling, and more.

SynAir-G dashboard communicates with a REST API web service that was built using the secure Django Framework. Django is a high-level Python web framework that encourages rapid development and clean, pragmatic design.

In relation to the storage capabilities, a MongoDB document database is used to store all the necessary configuration for the Synair-g app. The MongoDB was selected as it can provide many benefits to a software development team:

- It has a flexible schema making it easier to evolve and store data in a way that is easy for programmers to work with.
- It is also built to scale up quickly and supports all the main features of modern databases such as transactions.
- It provides various features, such as authentication, access control, encryption, to secure the MongoDB deployments.

5.4. Ingestion Service (Health Questionnaires)

A dedicated REST API endpoint is used for injecting the users' answers to the health questionnaire. The replies are captured within a JSON object, which is then transmitted to the backend for storage in MongoDB. A snapshot of an user response example is presented in the Figure 13.


```
_id : 64d0ad2ea13779890fefbc3a
questionnaire_name : health_questions
▼ questions [12]
  ▼ 0 {7}
    _id : 64d0ad2ea13779890fefbc3b
    order : 0
    ▼ translations [6]
      ▼ 0 {2}
        language : EN
        text : How are you today?
      ▶ 1 {2}
      ▶ 2 {2}
      ▶ 3 {2}
      ▶ 4 {2}
      ▶ 5 {2}
    ▼ choices [5]
      ▼ 0 {4}
        _id : 64d0ad2ea13779890fefbc3c
        is_selected :  true
        ▼ translations [6]
          ▼ 0 {2}
            language : EN
            text : Very Bad
          ▶ 1 {2}
          ▶ 2 {2}
          ▶ 3 {2}
          ▶ 4 {2}
          ▶ 5 {2}
        template_id : 64c79feaa6dad305fd34a347
      ▶ 1 {4}
      ▶ 2 {4}
      ▶ 3 {4}
      ▶ 4 {4}
```

FIGURE 13 SNAPSHOT OF A JSON CONTAINING A QUESTIONNAIRE RESPONSE

5.5. Security

The application was developed to work using Keycloak for authorization purposes. Keycloak is an open-source Identity and Access Management tool developed by the American software company Red Hat.

The user registration process has been designed using OAuth2 via Keycloak. The benefits behind are the following:

- It uses OpenID Connect which is a well-known standard
- It's open-source and free, unlike some of the competition (like Okta)
- It's well-known and battle-tested, and there aren't, in fact, that many solutions like that (we've considered Keycloak, Okta, and CAS, but we've had previous experience with that last solution and we decided we want something different)
- There are many examples of successful front-end and back-end integrations, Keycloak has a dedicated JavaScript library, and you can use universal libraries for Java
- It's easy to customize thanks to Java-based extensions
- There are many ready-made extensions on the Internet
- It fulfilled many of our project requirements out of the box
- It has an administrative panel by default
- Keycloak has a well-documented administrative API which you can use, for example, to manage users from microservices ¹

¹ <https://pretius.com/blog/keycloak-ss0/>

6. Deployment Information

6.1. Timeline

The application's development process embraced an iterative method, involving the release of various application versions. These versions underwent testing and received feedback from a dedicated team, which then informed the subsequent development stages.

In this regard, the below table summarizes the activities in relation to the design, development and testing of the application until its final delivery.

	2022				2023							
	S	O	N	D	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Preparation & planning phase												
Analysis of the app requirements												
Design of the application												
Analysis of the app requirements												
Design of the application												
Implementation phase												
App development												
Dashboard development												
Testing phase												
Alpha Testing (Internal -INLE)												
Beta Testing (External- All research centers, LTU)												

6.2. Testing

Internal Testing

The first version of the application has been delivered at the end of May 2023. The application was made available internally in INLECOM and specific process for feedback has been created. The overall internal testing phase lasted for two weeks and revealed a few bugs and update requirements, especially on the mini games' performance.

External Testing

Following the resolution of the abovementioned issues, a demonstration of the application to all research centers and LTU took place around mid-July.

Testing in 6 research centers

The second round of testing took place as a supervised activity and in a structured manner in order to gain valuable feedback from the users that was fed to INLECOM’s design team for the app finalization.

The overall test took place from the 13th of July 2023 until the 10th of August 2023.

NKUA coordinated the users’ recruitment process in collaboration with the other research centers. Each research center was requested to recruit a total of 5 children/users aged 8-10 years old, having as a primary objective to include symptomatic ones.

Testing in LTU

The testing that took place in Sweden, was coordinated by LTU and included a set of predefined users (children aged 9-10 years old).

The user recruitment process commenced with the initial release of the app in June, and children began interacting with the application during June and July 2023. The targeted number of users was 30, with 15 of them testing the app in English and providing feedback. The remaining 15 worked with the app in the Swedish language and subsequently completed the questionnaire. The game was then revised based on the feedback collected from the test users.

In regard to the public showcase of the app, LTU will be also organized an event as part of Researcher Day in Sweden, known as "Forskarfredag," scheduled for late September. During this event, 30 children are expected to attend and participate in testing the app. The session will commence with a 30-minute introduction to the project and the game. Subsequently, they will be divided into 6 groups of 5, engaging with different stages of the game for a duration of 90 minutes. Ultimately, the winning group will be rewarded.

Another event is also scheduled in Aarhus for November 2023, named "Next Generation Conference: Literacies of the Future." During this event, the SynAir-G app will be demonstrated and tested by children. This aspect is currently in the planning phase, and in September, we will determine the feasibility of allowing children to test the app in the English language.

Testing questions (EU survey)

When it comes to the testing process, LTU has developed a post-test questionnaire (see below), which was completed by each test user (i.e., kids with the assistance of their parents) after using the app for a specific period of time. The aim of the questionnaire was to collect structured feedback on the application features that were attractive to the users as well as the ones that further enhancements were needed. The answers were taken into account for the delivery of the final version of the SynAir-G application.

TABLE 5 FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRE

NO	Question
1	On a scale of 1 to 10, how would you rate your experience with the app's main game (exploring countries) in terms of ease of use, understanding and participation? (1 = Not at all easy, 10 = Extremely easy)
2	On a scale of 1 to 10, how would you rate your experience with the app's mini games in terms of ease of use, understanding and participation? (1 = Not at all easy, 10 = Extremely easy)

3	On a scale of 1 to 10, how enjoyable did you find the game's audio and sound effects? (1 = Not enjoyable at all, 10 = Highly enjoyable)
4	On a scale of 1 to 10, how engaging in general did you find the activities within the game? (1 = Not at all engaging, 10 = Extremely engaging)
5	On a scale of 1 to 10, how would you rate the ease of following the instructions for the activities/games? (1 = Very difficult to follow, 10 = Very easy to follow)
6	On a scale of 1 to 10, how much did the earned points, energy, etc. as rewards provide a sense of accomplishment? (1 = Very little sense of accomplishment, 10 = Strong sense of accomplishment)
7	Which mini game did you find most enjoyable? (Sort from highest to lowest)
8	On a scale of 1 to 10, how would you rate the occurrence of technical issues or errors while you were using the game? (1 = Frequent technical issues/errors, 10 = No technical issues/errors).
9	Please report any issues encountered. Options: game crashes, freezing, slow loading times, error messages, any other problems (open text).
10	On a scale of 1 to 10, how would you rate the overall visual design of the game? (1 = Very unappealing, 10 = Very appealing)
11	How frequently have you used the game? (Once a day, twice a day, more than twice a day, once every other day, once a week, did not use it, could not use it because of technical errors)
12	On a scale of 1 to 10, how satisfied are you with the variety of activities available in the game? (1 = Very dissatisfied, 10 = Very satisfied)
13	On a scale of 1 to 10, what is your overall impression of the game? (1 = Very negative, 10 = Very positive)

7. Data protection & privacy considerations

Since the application & the wearables handle data of EU citizens, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) was taken into account to ensure compliance with its requirements. In this context, the following have been taken into account for both solutions:

- **Data Minimization:** The app and the wearables are collecting only the data that is necessary for their functionality.
- **User Consent:** For the user participation in the cohort study, for the purpose of which the application and the wearables will be used, a consent form will be signed explaining the details of the study. In addition to that, a Terms and Conditions (Annex A) has been prepared for the said tools.
- **Purpose Limitation:** Data are collected for specific purposes connected with the project implementation and it will not be used for any other purposes without obtaining additional consent.
- **Data Security:** Security measures were implemented to protect user data from unauthorized access, breaches, and theft.
- **Anonymization and Pseudonymization:** The use techniques like anonymization or pseudonymization were performed to reduce the risk associated with handling personal data.
- **Data Retention:** Clear data retention policies have been established. The data will be stored only for as long as necessary and will be deleted when it's no longer needed.
- **User Tracking:** Since we are using tracking technologies, the consent form and the Terms and Conditions document are transparent about it and give users the option to opt out at any time.

8. Conclusions

The deliverable D2.2 for the SynAir-G project, has been pivotal in establishing the foundational elements required for the project's broader objectives. Within the context of improving the monitoring and understanding of indoor air pollutants' impact on children's health, this deliverable focused on developing and implementing a sentinel system that integrates wearable devices and a gamified application to collect and analyze health data.

The problem addressed by this deliverable centers on the need for continuous and accurate monitoring of children's health metrics, particularly in relation to their exposure to indoor pollutants. The objective was to create a system that not only captures this data efficiently but also engages young participants in a way that ensures high levels of participation and data accuracy.

The primary findings from this deliverable include the successful selection and implementation of the Garmin vívosmart 5 wearable device, which meets the project's stringent requirements for continuous health monitoring in children. The development of the "Save The World" gamified application further supports this by encouraging consistent user engagement through educational and interactive content. The application, developed using the Ionic framework, ensures cross-platform deployment and provides a secure user experience through the integration of Keycloak for authentication and authorization. This technical approach not only enhances the user experience but also ensures data security and privacy, which are critical for the project's compliance with GDPR.

The dashboard component of the sentinel system is another significant achievement. It offers robust management tools and visual analytics capabilities, allowing administrators, teachers, and research centers to monitor student progress and engagement effectively. The dashboard's ability to manage user accounts, including bulk creation and deletion, and its comprehensive visual analytics features, such as multi-day queries and real-time user engagement metrics, make it an essential tool for managing the project's data flow. Additionally, the secure authentication methods implemented through Keycloak ensure that only authorized personnel can access sensitive data, reinforcing the system's overall security.

The technical architecture, which includes components like the mobile app, the dashboard, and the MongoDB backend, is designed to be robust, scalable, and secure. The use of containerization through Docker ensures that the system is resilient and easily deployable across different environments. The iterative development process, which involved multiple rounds of internal and external testing, was crucial in refining the system, addressing bugs, and ensuring that the application meets the project's high standards for reliability and user satisfaction.

Also, careful attention is paid to GDPR compliance, ensuring that data minimization, user consent, and purpose limitation were rigorously applied. Techniques like anonymization and pseudonymization were implemented to protect personal data, and clear data retention policies were established to ensure that data is only kept as long as necessary.

However, the work was not without its challenges. As detailed in the "Wearable Devices" section, the reliance on consumer-grade wearable devices like the Garmin vívosmart 5 introduced certain limitations. These include a dependency on external APIs and potential data accuracy issues when compared to clinical-grade devices. Despite these limitations, the selected devices were deemed

suitable due to their robustness and the support provided by the manufacturer. Additionally, the "Gamified Application" section discusses the challenge of maintaining long-term user engagement. While the gamified approach has been initially successful, the document acknowledges the risk that the novelty of the application may wear off over time, potentially affecting sustained user participation. To mitigate this, a comprehensive engagement strategy and incentive structure were developed to encourage ongoing interaction.

In evaluating the results, the deliverable has largely met its objectives. The integration of the wearable devices with the gamified application has proven effective in capturing the necessary health data while maintaining participant engagement. The architecture of the system, particularly the use of Docker for containerization and MongoDB for data storage, has provided a solid foundation for reliable and scalable operations.

ANNEX A: Terms and Conditions

Terms and Conditions

Our Terms and Conditions were last updated on [DATE].

Please read these terms and conditions ("Terms", "Agreement") carefully before using this mobile application (the "Service" or the "App") operated by INLECOM INNOVATION ("us", "we", or "our", "the Company"), a company registered in Greece at Tatoiou 11 Kifisia, Athens 14561.

AND

this wearable (the "Service") operated by University of Patras ("us", "we", or "our", "the Company"), a university registered in Greece at University Campus Rio Patras, Rio Patras 265 04.

This Agreement sets forth the legally binding terms and conditions for your use of the SAVE THE WORLD application (the "Service" or the "App") and the wearables (the "Service").

IF YOU DO NOT AGREE WITH ALL OF THESE LEGAL TERMS, THEN YOU ARE EXPRESSLY PROHIBITED FROM USING THE SERVICES AND YOU MUST DISCONTINUE USE IMMEDIATELY.

OUR SERVICES

The information provided when using the Services is not intended for distribution to or use by any person or entity in any jurisdiction or country where such distribution or use would be contrary to law or regulation or which would subject us to any registration requirement within such jurisdiction or country. Accordingly, those persons who choose to access the Services from other locations do so on their own initiative and are solely responsible for compliance with local laws, if and to the extent local laws are applicable.

The purpose of our Services is related with your participation in a study, part of the SynAir-G program (GA 101057271), which will associate indoor air quality determinants and their interactions with health outcomes in school-age children. The SynAir-G child study is a real-life observational study with the aim of prospectively associate indoor air pollutant variability and potential synergies with general, respiratory, immune, and mental health outcomes in school children. The App supports the aforementioned study, by posing simple questions about the child's health and pairing the wearable devices selected by the cohort to each user.

ACCEPTANCE OF TERMS

a. By downloading and using the App/Service, you agree to be bound by these terms and conditions, as well as any applicable laws and regulations.

b. Supplemental terms and conditions or documents that may be posted on the Service are hereby expressly incorporated herein by reference. The Company reserves the right, in its sole discretion, to make changes or update these terms and conditions from time to time. Any changes will be available by updating the 'Last updated' date of these Legal Terms. It is your responsibility to periodically review

these Legal Terms to stay informed of updates. Your continued use of the app following such updates constitutes your acceptance of the revised terms.

c. These terms and conditions constitute the entire agreement between you and us regarding your use of the App and supersede any prior agreements or understandings, whether written or oral.

LICENSE

a. Subject to your compliance with these Legal Terms, including the 'PROHIBITED ACTIVITIES' section below, we grant you a non-exclusive, non-transferable, revocable license to use the App for your personal, non-commercial use or intended business purpose. You may not modify, distribute, sell, or exploit the App or any of its content for any commercial purpose without the prior written consent of the Company.

Except as set out in this section or elsewhere in our Terms, no part of the Services and no Content or Marks may be copied, reproduced, aggregated, republished, uploaded, posted, publicly displayed, encoded, translated, transmitted, distributed, sold, licensed, or otherwise exploited for any commercial purpose whatsoever, without our express prior written permission.

b. Our App/Service is provided on an "as-is" basis and we make no warranties or representations of any kind, either express or implied, regarding the use, performance, or functionality of the App/Service.

c. We reserve the right to change, revise, update, suspend, discontinue, or otherwise modify the Services at any time or for any reason without notice to you. However, we have no obligation to update any information on our Services. We will not be liable to you or any third party for any modification, price change, suspension, or discontinuance of the Services. We cannot guarantee the Services will be available at all times. We may experience hardware, software, or other problems or need to perform maintenance related to the Services, resulting in interruptions, delays, or errors. You agree that we have no liability whatsoever for any loss, damage, or inconvenience caused by your inability to access or use the Services during any downtime or discontinuance of the Services. Nothing in these will be construed to obligate us to maintain and support the Services or to supply any corrections, updates, or releases in connection therewith.

d. There may be information on the Services that contains typographical errors, inaccuracies, or omissions. We reserve the right to correct any errors, inaccuracies, or omissions and to change or update the information on the Services at any time, without prior notice.

e. You are solely responsible for ensuring that your device meets the minimum system requirements for using our App.

f. We reserve the right, but not the obligation, to: (1) monitor the Services for violations of these Legal Terms; (2) take appropriate legal action against anyone who, in our sole discretion, violates the law or these Legal Terms, including without limitation, reporting such user to law enforcement authorities; (3) in our sole discretion and without limitation, refuse, restrict access to, limit the availability of, or disable (to the extent technologically feasible) any of your Contributions or any portion thereof; (4) in our sole discretion and without limitation, notice, or liability, to remove from the Services or otherwise disable all files and content that are excessive in size or are in any way burdensome to our systems; and (5) otherwise manage the Services in a manner designed to protect our rights and property and to facilitate the proper functioning of the Services.

TERMINATION

The Company may terminate your access to the App/Service at any time without notice or liability.

These Legal Terms shall remain in full force and effect while you use the App/Services. Without limiting any other provision of these legal terms, we reserve the right to, in our sole discretion and without notice or liability, deny access to and use of the services (including blocking certain IP addresses), to any person for any reason or for no reason, including without limitation for breach of any representation, warranty, or covenant contained in these legal terms or of any applicable law or regulation. We may terminate your use or participation in the services or delete any content or information that you made available at any time, without warning, in our sole discretion.

USER CONTENT

You are solely responsible for any content you submit or post on the App/Service. You retain all ownership rights in your content, but by submitting or posting it, you grant INLECOM, University of Patras (UoP) and the cohort participating research centers a license to use, reproduce, modify, adapt, translate, create derivative works from, solely for the purposes described in the SynAir-G project listed in the consent form.

If you access the Services via the App, then we grant you a revocable, non-exclusive, non-transferable, limited right to install and use the App on wireless electronic devices owned or controlled by you, and to access and use the App on such devices strictly in accordance with the terms and conditions of this mobile application license contained in these Legal Terms. You shall not: (1) except as permitted by applicable law, decompile, reverse engineer, disassemble, attempt to derive the source code of, or decrypt the App; (2) make any modification, adaptation, improvement, enhancement, translation, or derivative work from the App; (3) violate any applicable laws, rules, or regulations in connection with your access or use of the App; (4) remove, alter, or obscure any proprietary notice (including any notice of copyright or trademark) posted by us or the licensors of the App; (5) use the App for any revenue generating endeavour, commercial enterprise, or other purpose for which it is not designed or intended; (6) make the App available over a network or other environment permitting access or use by multiple devices or users at the same time; (7) use the App for creating a product, service, or software that is, directly or indirectly, competitive with or in any way a substitute for the App; (8) use the App to send automated queries to any website or to send any unsolicited commercial email; or (9) use any proprietary information or any of our interfaces or our other intellectual property in the design, development, manufacture, licensing, or distribution of any applications, accessories, or devices for use with the App.

LINKS TO OTHER WEBSITES

Our App/Service may contain links to third-party web sites or services that are not owned or controlled by the Company. The Company has no control over, and assumes no responsibility for, the content, privacy policies, or practices of any third-party web sites or services. You further acknowledge and agree that the Company shall not be responsible or liable, directly, or indirectly, for any damage or loss caused or alleged to be caused by or in connection with the use of or reliance on any such content, goods or services available on or through any such web sites or services. We strongly advise You to read the terms and conditions and privacy policies of any third-party web sites or services that you visit.

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

The App/Service and its entire contents, features, and functionality (including but not limited to all information, software, text, displays, images, video, and audio, and the design, selection, and arrangement thereof), are owned by us, our licensors, or other providers of such material and are protected by copyright, trademark, and other laws of both Greece and foreign countries.

Our trademarks and trade dress may not be used in connection with any product or service without the prior written consent of the Company.

PRIVACY POLICY

a. Our App may collect personal information from you, such as your unique SynAir-G ID, answers to the questionnaires, health and biometric data from Garmin wearable devices or any other information that you provide to us. We will use this information only for the purposes of providing you with the app and the research conducted under the SynAir-G project (GA 101057271) that you are part of.

b. We will not share your personal information with any third parties without your consent.

c. By using the App, you agree to the privacy policy posted on the Services, which is incorporated into these Legal Terms. Please be advised the Services are hosted in Greece. If you access the Services from any other region of the world with laws or other requirements governing personal data collection, use, or disclosure that differ from applicable laws in Greece, then through your continued use of the Services, you are transferring your data to Greece, and you expressly consent to have your data transferred to and processed in Greece.

d. The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and UK GDPR require us to explain the valid legal bases we rely on in order to process your personal information. As such, we may rely on the following legal bases to process your personal information:

i) Consent. We may process your information if you have given us permission (i.e., consent) to use your personal information for a specific purpose. You can withdraw your consent at any time.

ii) Legitimate Interests. We may process your information when we believe it is reasonably necessary to achieve our legitimate business interests and those interests do not outweigh your interests and fundamental rights and freedoms. For example, we may process your personal information for some of the purposes described in order to:

1. To generate new knowledge on chemical and biological indoor air pollutants and their main sources, focusing on synergistic interactions affecting health outcomes, in children of different socioeconomic backgrounds across Europe.
2. To develop user- and environmentally friendly solutions for indoor air quality monitoring and timely interventions, including personalization for vulnerable populations
3. To disseminate the generated knowledge and potential solutions to public authorities, policy makers, consumer protection entities, patient associations and the society, in accessible and actionable formats, including databases, guidelines and air quality standards

PROHIBITED ACTIVITIES

a. You may not use the App for any illegal or unauthorized purpose, including but not limited to copyright infringement or the distribution of malware.

b. You may not engage in any activity that interferes with or disrupts the App, servers, or networks connected to the App.

c. More specifically, as a user of the Services, you agree not to:

- Systematically retrieve data or other content from the Services to create or compile, directly or indirectly, a collection, compilation, database, or directory without written permission from us.
- Trick, defraud, or mislead us and other users, especially in any attempt to learn sensitive account information such as user passwords.
- Content or enforce limitations on the use of the Services and/or the Content contained therein.
- Disparage, tarnish, or otherwise harm, in our opinion, us and/or the Services.
- Use any information obtained from the Services in order to harass, abuse, or harm another person.
- Make improper use of our support services or submit false reports of abuse or misconduct.
- You may not in the use of the App in any way, violate any laws or regulations in your jurisdiction.
- Engage in unauthorised framing of or linking to the Services.
- Upload or transmit (or attempt to upload or to transmit) viruses, Trojan horses, or other material, including excessive use of capital letters and spamming (continuous posting of repetitive text), that interferes with any party's uninterrupted use and enjoyment of the Services or modifies, impairs, disrupts, alters, or interferes with the use, features, functions, operation, or maintenance of the Services.
- Engage in any automated use of the system, such as using scripts to send comments or messages, or using any data mining, robots, or similar data gathering and extraction tools.
- Delete the copyright or other proprietary rights notice from any Content.
- Attempt to impersonate another user or person or use the username of another user.
- Upload or transmit (or attempt to upload or to transmit) any material that acts as a passive or active information collection or transmission mechanism, including without limitation, clear graphics interchange formats ('gifs'), 1x1 pixels, web bugs, cookies, or other similar devices (sometimes referred to as 'spyware' or 'passive collection mechanisms' or 'pcms').
- Interfere with, disrupt, or create an undue burden on the Services or the networks or services connected to the Services.
- Harass, annoy, intimidate, or threaten any of our employees or agents engaged in providing any portion of the Services to you.
- Attempt to bypass any measures of the Services designed to prevent or restrict access to the Services, or any portion of the Services.
- Copy or adapt the Services' software, including but not limited to Flash, PHP, HTML, JavaScript, or other code.
- Except as permitted by applicable law, decipher, decompile, disassemble, or reverse engineer any of the software comprising or in any way making up a part of the Services.
- Except as may be the result of standard search engine or Internet browser usage, use, launch, develop, or distribute any automated system, including without limitation, any spider, robot,

cheat utility, scraper, or offline reader that accesses the Services, or use or launch any unauthorised script or other software.

- Use a buying agent or purchasing agent to make purchases on the Services.
- Make any unauthorised use of the Services, including collecting usernames and/or email addresses of users by electronic or other means for the purpose of sending unsolicited email, or creating user accounts by automated means or under false pretences.
- Use the Services as part of any effort to compete with us or otherwise use the Services and/or the Content for any revenue-generating endeavor or commercial enterprise.
- Sell or otherwise transfer your profile.

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES

The App and its content are provided "as is" without warranty of any kind, either express or implied, including but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability, fitness for a particular purpose, or non-infringement.

You agree that your use of the services will be at your sole risk. To the fullest extent permitted by law, we disclaim all warranties, express or implied, in connection with the services and your use thereof, including, without limitation, the implied warranties of merchantability, fitness for a particular purpose, and noninfringement. We make no warranties or representations about the accuracy or completeness of the services' content or the content of any websites or mobile applications linked to the services and we will assume no liability or responsibility for any (1) errors, mistakes, or inaccuracies of content and materials, (2) personal injury or property damage, of any nature whatsoever, resulting from your access to and use of the services, (3) any unauthorised access to or use of our secure servers and/or any and all personal information and/or financial information stored therein, (4) any interruption or cessation of transmission to or from the services, (5) any bugs, viruses, trojan horses, or the like which may be transmitted to or through the services by any third party, and/or (6) any errors or omissions in any content and materials or for any loss or damage of any kind incurred as a result of the use of any content posted, transmitted, or otherwise made available via the services. We do not warrant, endorse, guarantee, or assume responsibility for any product or service advertised or offered by a third party through the services, any hyperlinked website, or any website or mobile application featured in any banner or other advertising, and we will not be a party to or in any way be responsible for monitoring any transaction between you and any third-party providers of products or services. As with the purchase of a product or service through any medium or in any environment, you should use your best judgement and exercise caution where appropriate.

GOVERNING LAW AND JURISDICTION

a. These Legal Terms are governed by and interpreted following the laws of Greece. If your habitual residence is in the EU, and you are a consumer, you additionally possess the protection provided to you by obligatory provisions of the law in your country to residence. INLECOM INNOVATION/UoP and yourself both agree to submit to the non-exclusive jurisdiction of the courts of Athens, which means that you may make a claim to defend your consumer protection rights in regards to these Legal Terms in Greece.

b. Any disputes arising out of or in connection with these terms and conditions shall be subject to the exclusive jurisdiction of the courts of Greece. The European Commission provides an online dispute

resolution platform, which you can access. If you would like to bring this subject to our attention, please contact us in the emails provided below.

INFORMATION SAFETY

We have implemented appropriate and reasonable technical and organizational security measures designed to protect the security of any personal information we process. However, despite our safeguards and efforts to secure your information, no electronic transmission over the Internet or information storage technology can be guaranteed to be 100% secure, so we cannot promise or guarantee that hackers, cybercriminals, or other unauthorized third parties will not be able to defeat our security and improperly collect, access, steal, or modify your information. Although we will do our best to protect your personal information, transmission of personal information to and from our Services is at your own risk. You should only access the Services within a secure environment.

LIMITATION OF LIABILITY

The Company shall not be liable for any direct, indirect, incidental, special, or consequential damages arising out of or in connection with the use or inability to use the app, even if the Company has been advised of the possibility of such damages.

INDEMNIFICATION

You agree to indemnify and hold the Company harmless from any claims, damages, losses, or expenses, including attorney's fees, arising out of or in connection with your use of the App or any violation of these terms and conditions.

If you have any questions or concerns about these terms and conditions, please contact us at contact@inlecom.gr.

If you have any technical questions or concerns about the collection of data from Garmin wearable devices, please contact the University of Patras, Greece, Primary investigator: prof Sotiris Nikolettseas, nikole@cti.gr.

If you have any questions or concerns about the research process please contact the local research centers:

- Greece: National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA), Department of Allergy and Clinical Immunology Unit, 2nd Pediatric Clinic, Primary investigator: Dr Paraskevi Xepapadaki, vickyxepapadaki@gmail.com
- France: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Montpellier, Primary Investigator: Isabella Annesi Maesano, isabella.annesi-maesano@inserm.fr
- Finland: University of Oulu, Department of Oulun Yliopisto, Primary Investigators: Tuomas Jartti, tjartti@utu.fi
- Georgia: Center for Allergy and Immunology Research, Primary Investigator: Maia Gotua, maiagotua@gmail.com
- United Kingdom: The University of Manchester, Department of Division of Immunology, Immunity to Infection and Respiratory Medicine, Primary Investigator: Angela Simpson, Angela.Simpson@manchester.ac.uk

